

The CK25 Corporate Knowledge Reference Dataset for Benchmarking Text 2 SPARQL Question Answering Approaches

Sebastian Tramp[✉] and René Pietzsch[✉]

eccenca GmbH
Hainstr. 8, 04109 Leipzig, Germany
sebastian.tramp|rene.pietzsch@eccenca.com

Abstract. Question answering over Linked Data / RDF-based Knowledge Graphs is a subdiscipline of Natural Language Processing. The specific challenge of Text 2 SPARQL focuses on translating natural language questions into SPARQL queries, a structured query language for interacting with RDF-based Knowledge Graphs. In this paper, we present a dataset consisting of a knowledge graph, an ontology, and a query catalog, which can be used as a reference for Text 2 SPARQL techniques such as LLM RAG-based approaches. The dataset was created for the First International TEXT2SPARQL Challenge, which we organized as part of the 4th International Workshop on LLM-Integrated Knowledge Graph Generation from Text (Text2KG) at the ESWC2025.

Keywords: Benchmark · Natural Language Processing · Question Answering · Knowledge Graphs · Large Language Models

1 Introduction

Text to SPARQL is a task that aims to automatically generate SPARQL queries which retrieve answers from RDF-based Knowledge Graphs. As pointed out in [2], the task of parsing natural language questions into structured queries is even more prevalent now, given the high potential that Large Language Models (LLMs) offer in Retrieval-Augmented conversational agents and the problems they face with using the correct information as context.

In order to support researchers of RAG-based systems with reference questions and queries for a Knowledge Graph with an industrial background, we present CK25, a Corporate Knowledge dataset which describes products, suppliers, and a corporate organization.

The dataset was created for the First International TEXT2SPARQL Challenge¹, which we organized as part of the 4th International Workshop on LLM-Integrated Knowledge Graph Generation from Text (Text2KG²) at the 22th European Semantic Web Conference (ESWC2025³).

¹ <https://text2sparql.aksw.org/>

² <https://aiisc.ai/text2kg2025/>

³ <https://2025.eswc-conferences.org/>

2 Ontology and Knowledge Graph

In order to demonstrate Knowledge Graph capabilities in an enterprise context, we created a small ontology to briefly describe industry-related terms, such as products, suppliers, and prices. This ontology consists of 13 classes with 30 properties and provides a lightweight domain overview with shallow complexity. A structural overview of the ontology is depicted in Figure 1.

In addition to that, we integrated and generated interlinked instance data together with the ontology. In its current state, the entire Knowledge Graph contains 2,648 classified resources and 27,147 statements.

3 Curated Questions

We demonstrated the capabilities of this Knowledge Graph with our Enterprise Knowledge Graph Platform eccenca Corporate Memory⁴ to many colleagues and potential customers. During these demonstration sessions, and with additional interviews, we collected a list of 15 initial questions, which we afterwards extended to a list of 50 questions, by combining different features and question areas. The goal was to cover most of the classes and properties, and to provide questions with different complexity and output types (boolean, lists, single entities, aggregations). We labeled all questions with additional keywords to be able to get an overview of the following facts for each question:

- Which **features** of the SPARQL language are used in the query?
- Which **classes** of resources are queried with the question?
- Which **properties** are used to answer the question?

A complete example of a description of a question that includes all metadata is shown in Figure 2. The YAML spec used is an extension of the JSON structure used in QALD-10 [1]. An overview of the SPARQL features required to answer a query and the number of queries that need these features can be seen in Table 1. The distribution of queries over the classes and properties used is depicted in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

4 Results and Conclusion

We briefly presented CK25, a Corporate Knowledge Benchmark dataset for measuring the quality of Text to SPARQL approaches. We see this work as an addition to existing DBpedia or WikiData based datasets and used it as a sidekick in the First International TEXT2SPARQL Challenge. The dataset is available at <https://github.com/eccenca/ck25-dataset>.

⁴ <https://documentation.eccenca.com>

Acknowledgments. This work was partially funded by the European Federation (grant number 01QE2429A) and the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (grant number 13XP5230N). In addition to that, this publication is based upon work from COST Action CA23147 GOBLIN - Global Network on Large-Scale, Cross-domain and Multilingual Open Knowledge Graphs, supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology, cost.eu).

References

1. Banerjee, D., Usbeck, R., Mihindikulasooriya, N., Singh, G., Mutharaju, R., Kapaniathi, P. (eds.): Joint Proceedings of Scholarly QALD 2023 and SemREC 2023 co-located with 22nd International Semantic Web Conference ISWC 2023, Athens, Greece, November 6-10, 2023, CEUR Workshop Proceedings, vol. 3592. CEUR-WS.org (2023), <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3592>
2. Strappazon, A., Granitzer, M., Egyed-Zsigmond, E., Mitrovic, J., Ben Amor, M.: Instruct-to-SPARQL: A text-to-SPARQL dataset for training Wikidata Agents. In: ACM SIGIR Conference on Human Information Interaction And Retrieval. ACM, ACM, Melbourne (AUS), Australia (Mar 2025). <https://doi.org/10.1145/nnnnnnn.nnnnnnn>, <https://hal.science/hal-04918564>

Appendix

SPARQL Feature	Questions	
	Count	%
SELECT	47	94 %
ORDER	15	30 %
LIMIT	13	26 %
GROUP	9	18 %
COUNT	8	16 %
FILTER	5	10 %
BIND	5	10 %
SUBSELECT	4	8 %
ASK	3	6 %
OPTIONAL	3	6 %
EXISTS	3	6 %
AVG	3	6 %
HAVING	2	4 %
MIN	2	4 %
MAX	2	4 %
ROUND	2	4 %
SUM	2	4 %
OFFSET	1	2 %

Table 1. SPARQL features needed to answer the questions.

Fig. 1. Structural overview on the dataset ontology.

```

- id: 12
  question:
    en: >
      Which supplier are available to deliver
      Compensators?
  features:
    - SELECT
  classes:
    - :Hardware
    - :ProductCategory
    - :Supplier
  properties:
    - :hasSupplier
    - :hasCategory
  query:
    sparql: |
      PREFIX : <http://ld.company.org/prod-vocab/>
      PREFIX i: <http://ld.company.org/prod-instances/>
      SELECT DISTINCT ?result
      WHERE
      {
        ?hardware :hasSupplier ?result .
        ?hardware :hasCategory i:prod-cat-Compensator .
      }

```

Fig. 2. Example question description with additional metadata.

Fig. 3. Number of questions per class.

Fig. 4. Number of questions per property.